
The Rebel as Individual in T.S Eliot's Murder in the Cathedral and John Osborne's Luther

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ABSTRACT

The two dramatic works under study, though written by two different authors with different backgrounds and experiences, explore a similar theme - that of the conflict between the individual and authority. While one mirrors the set-up in the Church of England, the other peeps into the inner workings of the Roman Catholic Church. In both plays, the conflictual theatres and the ways the concerned authorities are questioned or resisted by individuals are brought to the fore. The authors present us with principal characters who are not persuaded by the demands of authority, be they of the Crown or the Church, rather they insist that they have to be their own men. The conflict between these opposing tendencies is at the root of the moral foundation of the plays. However, the conflicts go beyond this surface appearance. There is a spiritual dimension to them. The study explores all this and also underlines the fact that both Becket and Luther who stood their grounds in their face-off with powerful institutions did not do so for their own sake. Rather, their defiance is meant to expose the hypocrisies that rule and reign in both temporal and spiritual institutions. Through such defiance, individuals are freed from dogmas or institutional inhibitions, or both. In the end, the authors present us not with characters who are slaves to authority, but with moral advocates who insist that authorities must live up to their billing and calling. Through these character portraits, we see individuals who, in their struggle, strive selflessly to achieve the restoration of the individuality and the essentially human in man.

KEYWORDS: Conflict, Defiance, Individual, Authority, Hypocrisy, Inhibitions

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BACKGROUND

It is important to state from the outset that the playwrights under study are modernist writers. This being the case, a proper understanding of their world views must necessarily take into consideration what they were reacting or responding to as modernists. Modernism in literature draws attention to the demarcation that came about in the nineteenth century between the old and the new order. This absolute demarcation was brought about by World War 1. Before the industrial revolution, society was stable. The world was as it was in the past. Things were not moving rapidly. But industrialization changed all aspects of society, including the scientific and intellectual spheres. Urbanization set in and the sense of cohesive community got lost. This brought about isolation. There was no more certainty and security.

This change in society took its toll on the theatre. There was reaction against the eighteenth century represented largely by the Romantics. Whereas the Romantics advocated that the language of poetry has to be rich and opulent, modernist writers were wary of this. They saw the blank verse of the Romantics as deadly formalistic and boring. Whereas Romanticism sees nature as an entity where man can dissolve himself, Modernism held instead that literature should deal with human issues. With this disposition, the theatre began to probe humanity. To capture reality, you have to capture the mind of man. This development brought about a new kind of literature.

T. S Eliot and John Osborne, the dramatists whose works are being examined here, are products of this new thinking in drama. Elliot, a theoretician and great critic, was one of the prime movers of modernism. He was a leading poet of the modern period. He was deeply religious. He defended the tenets of the official Anglican religion. Drama, for Eliot, is an important adjunct of poetry. Poetry, he says, is important because it elevates the human soul. It lifts the soul of man to the high religious point and to the high point of culture. It is a great purveyor of culture.

However, Eliot resorted to Poetic Drama when he realized that a lot of people did not like poetry. Poetic drama which was popularized by Christopher Fry exploits the resources of poetry in dramatic form.

In an essay, "The Possibility of a Poetic Drama", Eliot holds that drama, from the point of view of literature, is only one among several poetic forms. However, he sees drama as perhaps "the most permanent, is capable of greater variation and of expressing more varied types of society than any other"(Eliot 55). For him as well, "poetic drama is a conscientious attempt to adapt a true structure- Athenian or Elizabethan- to contemporary feeling. It appears sometimes as an attempt to supply the defect of structure by an internal structure"(Eliot 60). Eliot notes that while very few people treat art seriously, those who treat it solemnly "will continue to write poetic pastiches of Euripides and Shakespeare" (Eliot 63).

For Eliot, this medium was important because it makes poetry palatable to people. For this reason, he wrote all his plays in the form of poetry.

John Osborne, on his part, was known for his virulent criticism. He represents a new generation in the theatre as well as a new artist in the writing of drama. His works focus largely on protest against social stratification. He attacked social injustice vehemently through his rejection of convention. He was against the oppression of the lower by the higher. His language is a metaphor for the rejection of convention. It is a language that breaks all norms. He was iconoclastic in language use.

Alan Carter quotes Osborne as saying: "I want to make people feel, to give them lessons in feeling. They can think afterwards" (Carter 1).

For Carter, Osborne, going by the statement above, is reminding us that we are thinking animals and should be capable of imaginative response. He holds further that Osborne never directly attempted to cure evils or crusade for rights, but simply to provide experiences, to expose and to amplify, and to let us draw our own conclusions. Carter is of the view that for Osborne, the major problem facing mankind is "the right to be an individual, to live as one wishes to live in an environment which rarely affords full opportunity to do so"(Carter 5).

Osborne was the leader of the angry young men in the theatre who fought against the old order. "The Angry Young Men" was a group of iconoclastic dramatists who took the English theatre by storm in the twentieth century. They were British Novelists and playwrights who emerged in the 1950s and expressed scorn and disaffection with the established socio-political order in their country. They were impatient and resentful of what they perceived as the hypocrisy of the upper and middle classes. Their writings expressed raw anger and frustration over the failure of postwar reforms to meet exalted aspirations for genuine change.

Before the publication of *Look Back in Anger*, some critics attacked Osborne as "a ruffian and an intellectual upstart who was doing the unthinkable in the drawing room, threatening the good manners and comfortable illusions of middle class life" (Carter 11). In fact, with the publication of the play, Osborne became one of Britain's leading playwrights as well as the undisputed leader of "The Angry Young Men".

Upon the publication of his play, *Look Back in Anger*, the Royal Court Theatre's press agent described John Osborne as "an angry young man". The description was then extended to Osborne's contemporaries who expressed rage at the persistence of class distinctions. *Look Back in Anger* was the representative work of the movement. Books written by members of this group usually feature a rootless, lower-middle or working class male protagonist who views society with scorn and sardonic humor and may have conflicts with authority.

The angry band conceived of drama as a new weapon for the interpretation of society and exposition of injustices in the system. For them, drama as an art form must step out of the scroll so as to engage in social reconstruction. For Osborne, the tag, "The Angry Young Men" was "irksome...like being called the Walls Ice Cream Man" (Carter 11). With the publication of "*Look Back in Anger*", "The Angry Young Men" phrase caught up in the mass circulation newspapers in the English society of the time. The play stirred to life even that traditionally jaded first night audience with its energetic irreverence and biting rhetoric.

Eliot's *Murder in the Cathedral* and Osborne's "*Luther*" will be examined against this background.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

From the background to this study, it is evident that the plays under consideration are borne out of the responses of their authors to the time and age in which they found themselves. In other words, the plays are products of history. To situate this study in a proper historical context, it is imperative that we adopt the historical approach to criticism in the elucidation of the plays.

As an approach to criticism, historicism, as popularised by Matthew Arnold, is interested in the historical circumstances of the people about whom a work of art is written. It considers all factors of society as well as the background of the writer. In historical criticism, socio-economic and political considerations come into play. It urges the reader to identify with the intentions of the author by proposing the audience of the different periods as the standards of interpretation and evaluation.

According to F.W. Bateson, the "historical-sociological approach provides the critic with a factual structure to which he can attach his perceptions and generalisations"(Wellek 267). The approach, he further says, typifies and somehow summarises the society of its time. He calls it "the expression in language of social solidarity"(Wellek 267). In historicism, the need for relevance makes it mandatory to take historical facts into consideration in assessing the author's work and concerns. This is because a sense of history is important considering the fact that every age has its own sensibility.

Historical criticism then endeavours, as Hippolyte Taine says, to recover "from the monuments of literature, a knowledge of the manner in which man thought and felt centuries ago" (David & Schleifer 369). This approach to historical criticism thus defines literary interpretation on a genetic model, as an explanation of how a work's genesis in a historical situation brings the work into being a distinct aesthetic object.

In the view of Stephen Greenblatt, the historical approach to criticism is concerned with discovering a single political vision, usually identical to that said to be held by the entire literate class or indeed the entire population. This vision, he argues, can serve as a stable point of reference, beyond contingency to which literary interpretation can securely refer. Literature is conceived to mirror the period's beliefs, but to mirror them as it were, from a safe distance. (Davis & Schleifer 369).

Our choice of this critical approach is informed by some considerations. For instance, the historical approach to literary criticism will cast light on and clarify the text itself. This usually involves identifying a text's references to history - specific allusions to actual people, political events, economic development, and so on. This effort will help to locate the text as a historical phenomenon. The historical approach also helps to identify the author as an artist with a significant past and a predisposition to write in a certain manner. This will enable us to ascertain how a text reflects the historical forces that shaped it initially and to understand how a historical moment produced a particular work of literary art.

EXTERNAL ORGANIZATION OF THE PLAYS

The conflict between the individual and authority appears to be the major concern of Eliot's *Murder in the Cathedral* and John Osborne's *Luther*. But this is only on the surface. On a deeper examination, the plays say much more than this. In this essay, we shall first take a cursory look at the surface appearance of the plays before concerning ourselves with their underlying import.

Murder in the Cathedral is based on a historical incident – that of the relationship between Henry II of England who lived in the twelfth century and his Archbishop, Thomas Becket. Theocracy, the form of government then, was such that temporal and spiritual powers were lumped together. The Crown submitted to the Church, yet the political power of the country rested solely on the Crown. This arrangement was fertile for all forms of conflict. This reared its ugly head in *Murder in the Cathedral*.

In this play, we are faced with the disagreement between the crown and the clergy as to who should discipline an erring priest according to the Constitutions of Clarendon. While Henry II believed that it was his duty as the king to carry out this function, Archbishop Becket maintained that it was no business of the king, but that of the church.

Another bone of contention bordered on disputed coronation. The king wanted his son to be crowned. Becket turns this down. In spite of appeals for a change of mind, Becket remained defiant. The king thus decided to discipline him. Becket was exiled. He returned after six years but remained unrepentant. The king could not have this, so he blurted out. In response to the king's expostulation, some overzealous minds rushed into the cathedral where Becket was praying and murdered him. The play revolves around this story line.

Luther, on its part, has religious conflict as its take off point. In this play, as in *Murder in the Cathedral*, an individual stands against authority. He is Martin Luther, a stubborn iconoclast of lowly birth, resentful of authority and blind to compromise. He caused an international tumult with his attack on some religious practices especially the sale of indulgences. He has nailed his theses for disputation at the church door. The papacy sees his teaching as heretical and schismatic. He is ordered to recant. He puts his foot down. The Pope issues the Papal Bull of Demarcation against him. He is excommunicated. This is the story line of *Luther*.

This brief review accounts for the external organization of the plays under consideration. This is not, however, their major concern. What the story lines we have depicted do is that they shape the course of action of the plays.

MAJOR CONCERNS OF THE PLAYS

In *Murder in the Cathedral*, our perspective is focused on Eliot, his convictions and what he thought art can do. The play is a deeply religious one with Anglican point of view. Its major concern is that it expresses in a profound way the tenets of the Christian religion, of death and regeneration, of death and martyrdom, and of substance and shadow. To achieve much, Eliot compresses a number of dramatic forms. The most important here is the ritualistic nature of the play. This is in consonance with the Christian ritual of Christmas.

Ritual is integral to man and nature. It deals basically with the regeneration of life, the death and birth of life. Eliot uses it to reenact the idea of life and death in this play. He uses the idea of nature dying. The play starts in autumn, moves to winter, and then to summer. This is the ritual cycle of the play. The trajectory of the action of the play follows faithfully the idea of death, resurrection and life. This happening in nature is paralleled by the death and eventual martyrdom of Becket.

From this overview, it should be seen that it is more fulfilling to see the play as dealing with death and regeneration. This introduces us to the morality element of the play. It is a form of medieval drama dealing with death, sanctions or punishment. The Chorus give us a clear picture of this: that sin is rewarded with punishment and death.

The overall framework of the theme is cyclic. This follows from the design of the play. The message is that death and life are united. This is a strong Christian viewpoint. For Christians, death is not the end, it is the beginning. Just as Christ represents death and

resurrection, so does Becket in the play. Eliot uses Becket's last days to draw attention to the importance of Christian faith on human nature.

Another underlying nature of the play is its subtle comment on the nature of power. This is revealed through Becket. The second Tempter has come to tempt him, presenting him with the possibility of the restoration of his chancellorship with all its pomp and grandeur. Becket turns this down, pointing out that the whole question of power has to do with substance and shadow. The substance, the real power, he says, belongs to God. That of the king is temporal and temporary. It is shadowy; it is effervescent; it is a will-o-the-wisp.

Becket puts it thus:

Temporal power, to build a good world, To keep order, as the world knows order. Those who put their faith in worldly order, Not controlled by the order of God, In confident ignorance, but arrest disorder, Make it fast, breed fatal disease,... But what was once exaltation Would now only be mean descent (Eliot 40).

As Becket undergoes his suffering, an important Christian point is registered; that is that action does not constitute in physical action alone. Becket tells us that "... action is suffering/And suffering is action" (Eliot 32). We also learn from Becket's sermon that Christian martyrdom is not an accident. It is the design of God. Thus, when Becket dies, his death is not painful. It is the gateway to a new birth. It eventuates in the oblation of life.

A.G George, known for his critical study and analysis of Eliot's complex poetry through the exploration of his intellectual framework and cultural ideas, points to some existential motifs in the play. The most important for him is the tragic sense of life. Suffering is inescapable. It is universal. There is no remedy for it. All that man can do in his existential condition is to endure it. George observes that "this tragic sense" is antithetical to the belief in the explicability of suffering and in knowledge as a panacea for it" (Eliot 227). He believes that suffering is rooted in man's contingent nature. Thus, man's physical and religious duty consists in accepting his situation. This is what Becket does as he suffers.

Perhaps, the major concern of the play can be summed up in the words of T.S Eliot himself who said that his intention is to concentrate on death and martyrdom.

Luther is a reflection or re-enactment of John Osborne's artistic philosophy in *Look Back in Anger*. In the play, Luther, Osborne as an angry young man brings to full focus how an iconoclast can hold a mirror to society.

It has been noted that Martin Luther was brought into conflict with the authority. The major concern of this play lies in how Osborne exploits this surface structure of the play. He uses it to draw attention to what he considers the hypocrisy and evil practices in the Catholic Church. The theme being explored here has universal significance. It is as timeless and as relevant today as it was when Osborne wrote the play.

The most despicable of these practices was the sale of indulgences and relics. Indulgences are letters of pardon for committed sins and even for those yet to be committed, but which one intends to commit. They are even for the dead. Once purchased, says Tetzl, "the soul flies out of purgatory and sings"(Osborne 64).

Tetzl further tells his captive audience:

"I challenge any one here, any member of this audience, to present me with a sin, anything, any kind of a sin, I don't care what it is, that I can't settle for him with one of these precious little envelopes. Why, if any one had ever offered violence to the blessed Virgin Mary, Mother of God if he'd only pay up - as long as he paid up all he could - he'd find himself forgiven. You think I'm exaggerating? You do, do you? Well, I'm authorized to go even further than that. Not only am I empowered to give you these letters of pardon for the sins you've already committed, I can give you pardon for those sins you haven't even committed but which, however you intend to commit!"(Osborne 59).

Osborne finds this practice ridiculous and makes it the butt of his satirical searchlight. Another catholic theology which was in dispute was that of the sacraments. The priest celebrating the mass is empowered to turn the elements of the bread and wine into the actual substance of the Body and Blood of Jesus. Penance was regarded as a form of sacrament. A contrite sinner must confess his sins orally to a priest who would then impose penance on him. This would ensure his forgiveness and reinstate him in God's grace. Again, the Bible was seen as a sacred document reserved only for priests and their superiors. There was also the practice of the use of images in aid of worship. These were some of the corruptions in ecclesiastical society which Luther stood against.

At the beginning of the play, we are introduced to Luther as he joins the order of St. Augustine. He does menial jobs. Members of the Order, among other things, are under a vow to be poor. But no sooner had Luther joined this order than he discovered that the members do not live according to the injunctions of their calling.

Even more disturbing to Luther is the fact that those who feel as scandalized as he feels do not have the courage to speak up. Having decided to nail his theses for disputation, he complains thus:

There are some who complain of these things, but they write in Latin for scholars. Who'll speak out in rough German? Someone's got to bell the cat! For you must be made to know that there's no security, there's no security at all, either in indulgences, holy busywork or anywhere in this world. It came to me while I was in my towel, what they call the monk's sweathouse, the jakes, the John or whatever you're pleased to call it. (Osborne 75).

Osborne uses the character of Luther as a remarkable vehicle for the exposition of this double standard. He imbues Luther with a frame of mind that insists on the freedom of the individual spirit, a frame of mind that rejects "cant and rubbish". This explains why he refuses to recant his teachings. The Pope dismisses him as a "double-faced German bastard" (Osborne 95). The Papal bull of demarcation is issued against him. He is excommunicated.

On receiving his letter of excommunication, Luther blurts out thus:

I have been served with a piece of paper. Let me tell you about it. It has come to me from a latrine called Rome, the capital of the devil's own sweet empire. It is called the papal bull and it claims to excommunicate me, Dr. Martin Luther. These lies they rise up from paper like fumes from the bog of Europe; because papal decretals are the devil's excretals. I'll hold it up for you to see properly. You see the signature? Signed beneath the seal of the Fisherman's Ring by one certain midden cock called Leo, an over-indulged jakes attendant to Satan himself, a glittering worm in excrement, known to you as his holiness the Pope (Osborne 97).

The play is intended to expose the Catholic Church for what Osborne thinks it is. Luther, his spokesman, calls Rome a Latrine, the capital of the devil's own sweet empire. He calls the Papal decretals the devil's own excretals. Leo, who signed the letter of excommunication, is dismissed by Luther as an over-indulged Jake's attendant to Satan, a glittering worm in excrement.

The fundamental message of the play becomes fully appreciated through Staupitz, the Vicar General of the Order of St. Augustine, to which Luther belongs. He tells us what Martin Luther represents. Luther, he points out, was initially a frightened little monk who came to the Prior for blame or praise. But now, when he belches, the world stops what it is doing and listens.

Luther does not want to be a "fixed star", but a "shifting planet". Staupitz justifies Luther's stand. He believes that Luther has made a thing called Germany. He has "unlaced a language and taught it to the Germans and the rest of the world will just have to get used to the sound of it" (Osborne 121). He argues further that Luther has taken Christ away from the low mumblings and soft voices, and put him back where he belongs.

Thus, what the play does is that it challenges the dominance of the Roman Catholic Church which sees the Pope as the spiritual descendant of St. Peter, and as Christ's Vicar on earth. This is achieved by throwing open the skeleton in the cupboard of the Papacy. These evils in this system, Osborne suggests, remove the individuality of man. They kill the conscience of man. What Osborne does in this play is to restore the dignity of man. The restoration of the essentially human in man is his preoccupation.

For Alan Carter, Luther is one of Osborne's private voice plays. It is a play concerned with "a solitary figure, lost without purpose in an emotional void" (Carter 55). He believes that Osborne's heroes in his plays are worried by a breakdown in human communication. They suffer isolation and are alone in their awareness of what is wrong.

In *Luther*, Osborne tries to "balance the idea of man as an individual with that of man as part of society" (Carter 80). In the play, Osborne searches for identity and the refutations of the inherited traditions of life. Martin is symbolic of Osborne's grand design, the recovery of a personal belief and a private conscience. In fact, the animal imagery in *Luther*, Carter submits, is used to give a vivid expression to Martin's agony, both physical and spiritual, as he contemplates the nature of faith. Ultimately, Osborne's drama is full of conflict, generated by the inflexibility of both society and his characters.

CONCLUSION

From the foregoing, it can be seen that the plays mirror their age and time. Thomas Becket and Martin Luther are quintessential individuals who, through their insistence on propriety succeed in giving the authorities they faced a bloody nose. In *Murder in the Cathedral*, the individual has to accept suffering. It is like giving up oneself for the good of all as Christ did.

To be able to play this role, sacrifice is needed. You need to sacrifice your self for all like the sacrificial lamb. No compromises. The individual has to stand his ground in courage. If Becket kow towed to the king, the essence of his life will be lost.

In *Luther*, if Martin Luther did not insist on being himself, the corrupt practices and indulgences that he was up against will continue. He sacrificed so that the church could look itself in the mirror and make amends.

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